

IMPORTANCE OF SURGERY IN HOMOEOPATHY**Dr. Sudipta Pandit***

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Article Received on 23 Oct. 2025,
Article Revised on 13 Nov. 2025,
Article Published on 16 Nov. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17616724>

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How to cite this Article: Dr. Sudipta Pandit*. (2025). Importance Of Surgery In Homoeopathy. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 14(22), 652-656.

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ABSTRACT

In this article, you will learn and understand the significance of Surgery in Homoeopathy, how Surgery and Homoeopathy can complement each other to provide better treatment for surgical diseases and thus reduces the Global burden of disease to some extent. The conclusion of this article is very logical and clear that the integration of Surgery and Homoeopathy in health care facility is very essential as they complement each other.

KEYWORDS: homoeopathy, surgery, surgeon, treatment, diseases.

INTRODUCTION

According to a report by the Lancet Commission of Global Surgery 2015, more than 5-billion people worldwide lack access to affordable, safe, surgical care. Another report by the Lancet also stated that, "*about 30% of the global burden of disease*

could be surgical". At this point integration of Homoeopathy and surgery can work best to reduce the Global burden of disease to some extent.^[1]

In this aspect the significant role of surgery and homoeopathy in treating the surgical diseases is very crucial. How they can complement each other to improve health care issues related to surgical cases has been discussed below under few headings.

SURGERY: It is that branch of medicine that deals with Repairing, removing or replacing the diseases tissue i.e. any Cutting, suturing and repairing of human tissues.

Definition of Surgery: “a branch of medicine concerned with diseases and conditions requiring or amenable to operative or manual procedures”^[2] -(Merriam-Webster)

According to Britannica, Surgery is a: “*Branch of medicine that is concerned with the treatment of injuries, diseases, and other disorders by manual and instrumental means. Surgery involves the management of acute injuries and illnesses as differentiated from chronic, slowly progressing diseases, except when patients with the latter type of disease must be operated upon.*”^[3] - (Britannica)

The great Indian surgeon, Sushruta, defined “Ideal Surgeon” as, “A person who possesses courage and presence of mind, a hand free from perspiration, tremor less grip of sharp and good instruments and who carries his operations to the success and advantage of his patient who has entrusted his life to the surgeon. The surgeon should respect this absolute surrender and treat his patient as his own son.”^[4]

COMMON TYPES OF SURGERY^[5]

According to Degree of Risk

- Major surgery: Usually it involves high degree of risk.
- Minor surgery: it involves minimal risk.

According to Purpose

- Elective surgery.
- Urgent surgery.
- Emergent surgery.
- Required surgery.
- Diagnostic surgery.
- Corrective surgery.
- Reconstructive surgery.
- Procurement for transplant.
- Constructive surgery.
- Cosmetic surgery.

According to extent of surgery

- Simple surgery: It involves only the most affected areas.
- Radical surgery: The extensive surgery beyond the area obviously involved.

COMMON SURGICAL SPECIALITIES^[6]

1. General surgeon.
2. Colon and rectal surgeon.
3. Neurosurgeon.
4. Critical care surgeon.
5. Obstetrician and Gynecologist
6. Ophthalmologist.
7. Orthopedic surgeon.
8. Otolaryngologist (also known as ENT)
9. Pediatric surgeon.
10. Plastic surgeon.
11. Surgical oncologist.
12. Thoracic surgeon.
13. Urologist.
14. Vascular surgeon

The above mentioned specialists (surgeon) have their specific role in treating specific surgical cases respectively. But as a Homoeopath we have abundant scope which covers more or less all the field of surgery where we can work for treating surgical cases.

Homoeopathy and Surgery^[7,8]

Our master Hahnemann described about how to deal with such cases in Organon of Medicine. In §186- Master Hahnemann has discussed about the concept of LOCAL DISEASES. Here, which is called Local if it be very trivial and it is of no great moment.

If a person is subjected to any external injury, then the body reacts as a whole e.g. in the form of fever etc. *“The treatment of such diseases is relegated to surgery when affected parts require mechanical aid to remove external obstacles to cure.”*

Regarding the treatment few examples was mentioned in this aphorism like

- Reduction of dislocations (‘by needles’ in 6th edition)
- By bandages to bring together the lips of wounds (‘by mechanical pressure to still the flow of blood from open arteries’ in 6th edition)
- By extracting foreign bodies that have penetrated into the living parts.
- By making an opening into the cavity of the body to remove an irritating substance.

- □By reducing and fixing the fractured bones.

Importance of Surgery in Homoeopathy^[4,5,6,7]

1. To learn the Principles of surgery.
2. To acquire knowledge about the fundamental of examination of surgical cases.
3. To acquire knowledge about the use of standard instruments for examination of a case, asepsis, dressing, plaster, antisepsis etc.
4. It also includes study of radiology, which is helpful for diagnostic purpose, prognostic purposes as well as plan for surgical intervention and management of a case.
5. It includes orthopaedic, dental, ENT, ophthalmologist, neonatal surgery.
6. Pre-operative and post-operative intervention of Homeopathic medicine is helpful to relief the suffering of the patient. Some commonly used homoeopathic drugs for these purpose are Arnica, calendula, Hypericum, Staphysagria, Cantharis, Belladonna, Hepar Sulph., Silicea etc.
7. There are some surgical diseases which can be cure by Homoeopathy (e.g.- boils, carbuncle, cysts, ulcers, wound, hydrocele, warts etc.) with the proper knowledge of the Subject.

Significance of Surgery

- To remove the foreign body.
- When the disease has progressed and lead to pathological changes that required surgical intervention.
- To save the life of the patients in acute emergencies.
- In a condition when only medicine can't bring back the patients to their healthy state without surgical intervention.
- In case of trauma or accidents, when homoeopathic medicine do not have the time to act.
- For sterility, D & C operation.

DISCUSSION

Integration of surgery and homoeopathy for the treatment of surgical cases, can offer better outcome, and hence it can reduce the global burden of surgical diseases to some extent. Homeopathy has many important drugs that can work as good as other drugs, in fact in some cases it can work even better. There are many evidences of such cases. We can think uses of

Homoeopathic drugs as pre-operative as well as post-operative in modern set up in hospitals, health care institutions.

CONCLUSION

It is very obvious that, Surgery can't replace Homoeopathy, nor Homoeopathy can replace surgery, but their combine treatment when required can bring about positive outcome for those surgical cases. Therefore, the conclusion is very logical and distinct that the integration of Surgery and Homoeopathy in health care facility is very essential as they complement each other. We should always keep in mind, that it is very important to focus on the patient's improvement as a whole, in a holistic approach as taught in our Homeopathic principles.

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